

COMPRESSIVE FAILURE OF 2D WOVEN COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

This paper presents experimental and numerical research on the compressive failure of orthogonal 2-D woven composites with different stacking emphasizing the role of the interlacing region of tows. Resulting optical micrographs demonstrate the influence of the support of adjacent layers on the sequence of events leading to failure of woven composites.

Keywords: Compressive failure, 2D woven, textile composites, stacking, FEA

INTRODUCTION

When examining a cross-section of a woven laminate, the variability of the microstructure is observed to be significant. This variability can include for example a random shift of adjacent layers, a variation of the shape of the tows and their paths, amongst others. Isolating and experimentally studying the effect of each of these variables on the compressive strength is not trivial. Although some work can be found in literature concerning the compressive failure of woven composites [1,2,3], virtually none explicitly studied the effect of variations of the reinforcement geometry on the resulting damage mechanisms. At the laminate level, the effect of stacking/nesting on the failure strength was reported to be as high as 30% [4], making stacking one of the more significant variables influencing the compressive failure strength of a laminate, Figs. 1a and 1b.

At the layer level, it is generally accepted that the poorer in-plane properties of 2D woven composites, relative to unidirectional (UD) ones, originate from the fibre crimping introduced by the interlacing of the tows. The understanding of the interlacing region's behaviour and its role on failure is thus a key issue in the failure prediction of woven composites.

In the present work, the effect of ply stacking on the compressive damage mechanisms under uniaxial load is studied. Particular attention is given to the behaviour of the crimp region of the load-aligned tows; which is defined as the region where the load-aligned tows go from under (over) to over (under) the transverse tows, Fig. 1c.

a) Random-Stacking. b) Ordered-Stacking c) Crimp region

Figure 1: Influence of stacking on microstructure and crimp region

EXPERIMENTS

The experiments consisted of compressively loading reduced Compact Compression (rCC) specimens. While in standard unnotched compression tests, specimens fail catastrophically, rCCs fail through the propagation of a crack starting at the notch tip. This type of failure allows the damage propagation and mechanisms to be studied in detail.

Manufacture

The carbon-epoxy prepreg used is a 2×2 twill, T300/920CX and a 5-Harness (5H) satin AGP280-5H, both manufactured by Hexcel, Fig. 2. They were cured in an autoclave following the manufacturer instructions. The thickness of a cured ply is nominally 0.25 mm for both laminates. After curing, the quality of both plates was inspected using C-scan.

a) 5H satin b) 2×2 twill

Figure 2 : Weave pattern the 2D woven composites tested

For each material, two plates of 12 plies each were manufactured:

1. Ordered-stacked: All plies were laid-up with the same orientation, 0° warp aligned. When laying-up, the Unit Cells (UC) of each ply were carefully positioned on top of the corresponding UCs of the previously laid plies, Fig. 3. To facilitate this, the cutting of the prepreg plies was made tow-number-wise and not dimension-wise. Additionally, pins were used to fix the plies at defined positions.
2. Random-stacked: All plies were laid-up with the same orientation, 0° warp aligned. When laying-up, the relative positions of the adjacent unit cells were not considered, leading to random shifts between layers, Fig. 4.

Figure 3: Ordered-stacking

Figure 4: Random-stacking

Testing

The rCC specimens were loaded in compression using the rig shown in Fig. 5a. In each test, after the crack propagated from the notch tip, the test was stopped, and the specimen removed from the clamp and potted in resin. Once hardened, the potted specimens were grinded and polished as indicated by section TT in Fig. 5b. Using an optical microscope, the successive through-thickness sections (TT), from the edge of the specimen towards the notch, were inspected for damage.

a) rCC Rig

b) rCC Specimen

Figure 5: rCC rig and specimen dimensions

RESULTS

The comparison between the damage mechanisms of ordered-stacked and random-stacked specimens of the two laminates manufactured is now presented in detail.

In the 2×2 twill case, the random-stacked specimens show a through-thickness crack propagating through the kinking of the load-aligned tows and matrix cracking, Fig.

6a. The failure morphology of the ordered stacked specimens is significantly different; besides matrix cracking and kink-band formation, delamination and pronounced yarn bending can also be found, Fig. 6b.

Figure 6: Comparison between the damage morphology of the random-stacked and of the ordered-stacked specimens for the 2×2 twill case

In Fig. 7, these differences are observed in more detail. It is possible to see that the delamination found in the ordered-stacked specimens is connected to the pronounced bending of the longitudinal tows without kinking, and that it occurs at the crimp regions. In the random-stacked specimens, the bending of the load-aligned tows is significantly less. Additionally, the effect of the reinforcement geometry, namely the crimp region, on the damage morphology is less evident.

Figure 7: Details of the random-stacked and ordered-stacked failure morphology for the 2×2 twill case

For the 5H satin laminate, the differences between the random-stacked and the ordered-stacked are less pronounced, Fig. 8. In both cases, the failure morphology is composed by matrix and transverse tow cracking, and kink-band formation. No visible damage concentration at the crimp regions can be found in the embedded layers. Nevertheless, and contrary to the 2×2 twill case, the surface ply of several specimens (both random and ordered-stacked) shows damage concentration at the interlacing region, Fig. 9.

Figure 8: Comparison between the damage morphology of the random-stacked and of the ordered-stacked specimens for the 5H satin case

Figure 9: Damage concentration at the interlacing region in the outer ply of a random-stacked 5H satin specimen

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Finite Element Models (FEM) of the two weaves were built. The goal was to obtain qualitative insight on the deformations of the two weaves that could help explain the experimental results obtained. Tows and matrix were modelled as transversely orthotropic and isotropic materials respectively. A voxel FEM was obtained as in ref. [5]. Periodic Boundary conditions were applied to the Translational reduced Unit Cells (TrUC) of both weaves.

The TrUC concept enables the analysis of a representative domain smaller than the UC. Analyzing Fig. 10a, it is possible to recognise that the entire weave geometry can be re-constructed by spatially translating the unit cell E1 in an orthogonal way. Similarly in Fig. 10b, it is possible to reconstruct the entire weave geometry by spatially translating the subcell E1 in a non-orthogonal way. Using the Equivalent Subcell principle, presented in [6] and further explored in [7], the periodic displacement boundary conditions for this subcell can be obtained.

A linear elastic analysis was performed; the qualitative results for the deformed shapes of the two weaves upon compressive loading are shown in Figs. 11c and 12c.

Figure 10: Comparison between the Unit Cell and Translational reduced Unit Cell of 2x2 twill

Figure 11: Numerical analysis of a 2x2 twill

Figure 12: Numerical analysis of a 5H satin

ANALYSIS

Failure loci

Regions of high tow angular misalignment relative to the direction of the applied loading are likely failure loci. Analyzing the deformed shape of the 2×2 twill weave, it is possible to see the crimp regions are the regions of higher tow misalignment. Also in the 5H satin, significant rotation will occur at the crimp regions. However, in the 5H satin case, other regions of the weave suffer significant rotation; see light circles in Fig. 12c. In addition to the crimp regions, also these will constitute potential failure regions. These additional potential failure initiation regions will contribute to a decrease in the likelihood of failure occurring solely at the crimp regions.

Ordered-stacked v.s. Random-Stacked

The difference between the failure morphology of the 2×2 twill random-stacked specimens and the ordered-stacked ones can be attributed to the variation in the support provided by the neighbouring plies. Fig. 13a shows an idealised load-aligned tow. The arrows indicate its anticipated deflection direction due to the applied load. Fig. 13b shows the same yarn, together with two adjacent yarns, in an ordered stacked laminate. It can be observed that the anticipate displacement of the tows are all compatible and in phase. Fig. 13c shows the same yarn but now in a random-stacked laminate. In contrast to the observed in Fig. 13b, the anticipated displacements in Fig. 13c are not compatible. In this case the adjacent tows will act to reduce the deflection of the embedded load-aligned tow, providing increased support. Additionally, in the random-stacked case, the adjacent transverse tows (dashed) might replace the matrix near the interlacing regions due to nesting, while in the ordered-stacked this area will be surrounded by pure matrix.

In the 5H satin case, the differences between ordered-stacked and random-stacked specimens' failure morphologies could not be clearly observable.

Figure 13 Effect of stacking on the interaction between yarns during compression.

5H satin v.s. 2×2 twill

As discussed in the previous section, the failure morphology for the 5H satin was relatively similar for the ordered-stacked and random-stacked specimens. For the 2×2 twill, the FEM results (Figure 11c) show that the crimp region is the one that rotates the most. This can be associated with the anti-symmetry verified at this region, as idealised in Figure 14a. In contrast, for the 5H satin, the FEM results (Fig. 12c) show that regions other than the crimp region also rotate significantly. This can be associated with the lack of anti-symmetry at the crimp region, Fig. 14b.

When coupled with the experimental findings (damage morphology less significantly affected by ordered v.s. random-stacked, see Fig. 8), these observations point towards the 5H satin weave being less affected by the adjacent layers' support variation than the twill. Nevertheless, the surface layer (less supported) of several 5H satin specimens (ordered and random-stacked) showed damage concentration at or nearby the crimp region. These findings demonstrate that, also the damage morphology of the 5H satin weave is affected by the support of the adjacent layers.

Figure 14 Difference in behaviour between the 2×2 twill and the 5H satin stacked laminates upon compression

CONCLUSIONS

The compressive damage mechanisms of random-stacked (random shift between UCs in adjacent layers) and ordered-stacked (superposed UCs) laminates of two different 2D woven composites were experimentally studied.

The experimental findings show that for the 2×2 twill case the damage mechanisms of random and ordered-stacked specimens are substantially different. In the ordered-stacked specimens, additionally to kink-band formation and matrix cracking, delamination associated with significant yarn bending can be found. This difference is attributed to the decrease in support provided by the adjacent plies when compared to the random-stacked case. The increased support provided by the adjacent plies in the

random-stacked case is a result of two main factors: (i) support provided by the adjacent tows, (ii) replacement of resin rich areas by the transverse tows, due to nesting near the crimp region.

Due to the asymmetric structure of the 5H satin weave, damage concentration at the crimp region was not observed. The numerical analysis shows that other regions of the weave besides the crimp region are likely to be failure locus. Both experimental observations and the numerical results suggest that the 5H satin weave tested is less influenced by support of the adjacent layers than the 2×2 twill.

In a woven laminate, the layers at the surface will have one unsupported side. The observed importance of the support in the 2×2 twill case and the damage concentration at the interlacing regions observed in the outer plies of 5H satin specimens, suggests that the crimp regions at the surface plies are critical areas, i.e. potential failure initiation loci.

In a random-stacked laminate, local regions of ordered stacking will still exist. Their number and localization will vary from laminate to laminate and with lay-up procedure. This is expected to affect the laminate properties.

Finally, the results obtained also question the use of single ply meso-scale (tow/matrix level) FEMs to predict the compressive failure strength of woven laminates, as the influence of the adjacent plies is shown not to be negligible.

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